

Gross Anatomy of the Tongue of Camel

P. Jagapathi Ramayya¹, A. Prasanth Babu, S. Dhilleswara Rao,
J. Bhagya Lakshmi and H. S. Patki

Department of Veterinary Anatomy, College of Veterinary Science, Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University, Tirupati 517502, Andhra Pradesh

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The gross anatomy of the tongue of different ruminants has been studied (Gupta *et al.*, 1989). However, the information on the tongue of camel is found to be scarce. The present study was under taken to elucidate the number and distribution of papillae on the tongue of camel.

Materials and Methods

In the present investigation, tongues of three adult camels which were brought to the Department of Veterinary Pathology, College of Veterinary Science, Tirupati for postmortem examination were utilized. Tongues were collected immediately after death by separation from the floor of the oral cavity and were preserved in 10% neutral buffered formalin. After subjecting to proper cleaning gross features of the tongues were noted.

Results and Discussion

The tongue of camel consisted of three parts *viz.* apex or tip, the middle part or body and caudal part or root.

The tongue was extended from the rostral part of the floor of the mouth cavity to the oropharynx. It measured 40 cm in length. The width at the apex, body and *torus linguae* was almost 4.0cm, 6.0cm and 9.5cm respectively. These findings were in accordance with Pawan Kumar *et al.* (1995) in camel. They reported that in camel, tongue was 39.44 cm in length with maximum width at the root of 6.5 to 8.5 cm. They also noted that, the rostral part of the tongue was free and the remaining part was

attached to the floor of the mouth cavity by *frenum linguae*. The free portion measured one third in buffalo (Dhingra and Barnwal, 1979).

The apex of the tongue was flattened and showed dorsal and ventral surfaces. However apex of the tongue was pointed in cattle and a free flattened apex with notch at the centre was noticed in goat (Qayyam and Beg, 1975). The apex of the tongue in camel showed a sulcus (Pawan Kumar *et al.*, *loc.cit.*).

The body was wider than the apex. The caudal part of the body of the tongue formed elliptical prominence called *torus linguae*. In the present study no *fossa linguae* was observed in front of the *torus linguae* in camel. The tongue of the camel showed filiform, fungiform, conical, lenticular and circumvallate papillae. The dorsal surface of the tongue was rough due to filiform papillae. They were sharp, thread like and directed caudally.

The fungiform papillae of the camel were club shaped and were distributed in isolated manner over the apex and body of the tongue. In the present study no fungiform papillae were noted on *torus linguae*. Pawan Kumar *et al.*, (*loc.cit.*) also noted linearly arranged fungiform papillae in 2-3 rows on the ventral surface of the tip of the tongue in camel.

Lenticular and conical papillae were reported on the dorsum of the tongue especially on the *torus linguae*. The Lenticular papillae were distributed centrally whereas conical papillae were present on the periphery.

¹Corresponding author : Email : drjagapathi_palla@yahoo.com

Fig 1. Photograph showing Apex (A), Body (B), Root (R) and Torus linguae (T) of the tongue of camel

Fig 2. Photograph showing Conical (C), Lenticular (L) and Circumvallate (V) papillae on tongue of camel

Circumvallate papillae of camel were oval shaped, rounded at its free surface and were surrounded by a trench. They were arranged linearly in a single row on either side of the torus linguae. The number of papillae were 4-5 on either side. The average width and length of the circumvallate papillate was 0.62 and 0.87 cm on right side and 0.56 and 0.80 cm on left side. These papillae were surrounded by a slightly elevated mucosal ring. The average width and length of the papillae with mucosal ring was 1.07 and 1.35 cm on right side and 1.00 and 1.28 cm on left side.

Summary

The tongue of camel consisted of apex, body and the root. The total length of the tongue was 40

cm and the maximum width was noticed at the level of *torus linguae*. The *fossa linguae* was absent. Dorsal surface of the tongue showed filiform, fungiform, lenticular and circumvallate papillae. The number of circumvallate papillae was observed to be 4 on right side and 5 on left side on caudolateral aspect of the tongue. Foliate papillae were absent in the tongue of the camel.

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